

Standard Operating Procedures for **Clinical Data Acquisition**
Accelerating Medicines Partnership® SCHIZOPHRENIA
Proof of Principle (PoP) Trial MT1988

Version 1: September 26TH, 2025

Participant Population

Description

Clinical High Risk (CHR) participants are to be between the ages of 17 and 30 years of age at enrollment.

Schedule of Events, Recruitment, and Inclusion/Exclusion Criteria: see protocol

Instrument Administration

General Procedures

The Research Assistant/Coordinator (RA) will arrange a time to meet with the participant (and parent/guardian if the participant is a minor) to carry out the consent process. After consent/parental permission is obtained, they will meet with the participant to conduct the screening visit. The RA will complete all screening assessments. If the participant meets eligibility criteria after screening, the RA may proceed to scheduling the baseline assessment, following the ProCAN Central Rater Scheduling procedures below.

For most measures, ratings will be entered directly into REDCap during the visit. For measures that require notetaking and consideration prior to making a rating, the following procedures will be followed: During the visit, the RA or clinical rater will enter their notes into a free-text box for the measure in REDCap. These notes will be saved in the REDCap form and the RA or clinical rater will later review the notes to make their ratings. The ratings will then be entered into the appropriate fields in the REDCap form. Ratings should be entered into the form within 1 day of the clinical rating, except for the PSYCHS which may require consultation on the weekly consensus call and then will be entered or edited immediately following the call. The original notes in the free-text box cannot be deleted; this is the original source of the data collected and will be cross-checked by the on-site study monitor.

Local Site Completed Measures

- Medical/Psychiatric History

RAs will collect medical and psychiatric history via participant interview and review of medical records if available; the PI and prescriber should review these records which will need to be confirmed for eligibility.

- Demographics

Demographics will include age, sex, gender, race, ethnicity, socioeconomic status, employment, educational attainment and age and education of biological parents. The demographics will also ask whether the participant has a biological sibling participating in the study.

- Inclusion/Exclusion criteria

An interview will be conducted to assess inclusion/exclusion criteria according to study protocol as listed above.

- Enrollment Note.

The RA will complete the enrollment note form in ReDCap detailing informed consent procedures for each participant.

- Screening Physical Examination

The physical examination is to be conducted by the PI and/or prescriber and results are to be recorded in the REDCap system. The PI and/or prescriber will need to sign the physical exam in the REDCap system.

Any clinically significant findings should be added to the participant medical history.

- **Suicidality**

The CSSRS will be used to assess suicidal ideation and history of suicide attempts.

- **Urine tox screen**

The RA will indicate results of urine drug screen for each participant.

- **Lifetime AP exposure**

The lifetime antipsychotic exposure screen test will be conducted by the RA at screening.

- **Baseline Day 1 and Week 8 Physical Examination**

The PI or prescriber will conduct a follow-up physical exam. Any new signs and symptoms, and/or resolution of changes from a previous physical exams will be recorded. Any clinically significant change from baseline may also be considered an AE.

- **Concomitant medication.**

RA will record dose, frequency, administration, and dates of any concomitant medication; the prescriber should review these records in REDCap.

- **Randomization**

Subjects will be randomized within REDCap.

- **IMP dispensing/administration**

The RA will record date of dispensation, date of return, number of pills taken and number of pills returned.

- **Post dose observation**

The post dose observation form will be completed by the RA to indicate if participant completed the four-hour post-dose observation and if any adverse events were reported during this time.

- **Adverse events**

The PI and/or prescriber will record grade, organ class, and code for all adverse events reported in their visit progress note.

- **Pregnancy Point of Care**

The RA will record if pregnancy test was taken and the results of the pregnancy test.

- **Psychoeducation**

The RA will record date and completion status of psychoeducation sessions.

- **Recruitment Source**

The recruitment source form will be completed by the RA to detail how the participant was recruited into the study.

- **Missing Data**

The RA will record any missing data in the schedule of assessments for each visit.

- **Status form**

The RA will record any screen failure, study completion status, withdrawal, and reasons for withdrawal

from study.

- **Conversion Form**

The RA will record date of conversion, how conversion was determined, and diagnosis for any conversions in the study.

- **Participant de-brief**

At the end of their study participation, participants will undergo a debrief with the site investigator or designee, to be able to share their study experience and ask any questions.

Notes outlining the content of the session and any concerns which arose will be documented on the relevant clinical record.

Clinical Rating Scales

- **PSYCHS-CT**

Psychosis spectrum symptoms will be assessed with the *Positive Symptoms and Diagnostic Criteria for the CAARMS Harmonized with the SIPS* (PSYCHS) interview, adjusted for the clinical trial (CT). The PSYCHS-CT will be audio recorded in Zoom according to the Team H Speech/Language SOP.

- **Negative Symptom Inventory-Psychosis Risk (NSI-PR)**

Negative symptoms will be assessed utilizing 11 items from the Negative Symptom Inventory- Psychosis Risk which assess the 5 NIMH consensus domains (anhedonia, avolition, asociality, alogia, blunted affect). The NSI-PR will be audio-recorded in Zoom according to the Team H Speech/Language SOP.

- **PANSS**

The Positive and Negative Syndrome Scale (PANSS) will be used to assess and rate positive and negative symptoms and general psychopathology.

- **Calgary Depression Scale for Schizophrenia (CDSS)**

Depression will be assessed utilizing the Calgary Depression Scale for Schizophrenia (CDSS)

- **Overall Anxiety Severity and Impairment Scale (OASIS)**

The self-report Overall Anxiety Severity and Impairment Scale (OASIS) will be used to assess anxiety severity.

- **Perceived Stress Scale (PSS)**

The PSS is a self-report measure of the degree to which situations in one's life are appraised as stressful. Items were designed to tap how unpredictable, uncontrollable, and overloaded respondents find their lives.

- **8 - item PROMIS for sleep**

This is used to measure self-reported perceptions of sleep quality, depth, and restoration within the past seven days. This includes perceived difficulties falling asleep and staying asleep, as well as sleep satisfaction.

Training and Support

Staff Qualifications

All staff involved in recruitment and assessment of research participants will have completed required regulatory training and appropriate training in recruitment and assessment procedures. Psychiatric assessment is the equivalent of a physical exam, tailored to evaluate a patient for psychiatric pathologies. A good mental health assessor should have experience relevant to the person's condition. A good mental health assessor is credentialed in the instrument that they are administering. A good mental health assessor maintains boundaries appropriate for the assessment and conducts a culturally sensitive evaluation.

Conducting a risk assessment requires a high level of sensitivity not only to existing symptoms but to the normal course of development of young people and to the gradual change in their psychosocial functioning.

Professionals must have an understanding of the array of presentations of psychotic disorders, the natural history of a psychotic episode including the prodromal, active, and recovery phases, and proficiency in performing a psychiatric assessment. A good assessment in early psychosis is an ongoing process, allowing for the fact that symptoms are fluid and change over time.

Requirements for Certification: (1) A degree in psychology or a related field (e.g., social work, family therapy) or the equivalent of education and experience. (2) Familiarity with psychosis risk spectrum disorders. (3) The ability to conduct a culturally sensitive psychiatric assessment. (4) Familiarity with conducting psychiatric evaluations. (5) Completion of a Good Clinical Practice (GCP) training course that meets local IRB requirements. (6) Certification in the assessment that they are using. Training and certification procedures for each clinical rating school are detailed below.

Training and Certification Procedures

ProCAN leadership has discussed the implementation of training across the network. The network will be responsible for ensuring that staff sign up for the necessary training, complete all aspects of that training and are competent to carry out study procedures and assessments. They will ensure that appropriate support and additional training is provided in an ongoing way throughout the study. Experienced trainers have been allocated to the various measures to ensure accurate and consistent administration and scoring.

Outcome measures include clinical interviews in which the rater asks the questions and self-reports that are completed by the participant. Local assessors at each site will conduct the PSYCHS interview at the screening visit, while central clinical raters will conduct the PSYCHS at the remaining visits. and all other clinical rating scales. Training will occur for all clinical measures and all raters will be required to achieve certification of training for all measures for which they will be responsible. This will ensure that they have completed the necessary training and met acceptable reliability on each of the measures. Documentation of certification on each measure that requires certification will be recorded by the coordinator for the Network and only certified raters will be allowed to conduct the necessary assessments. Each site will not be activated to start recruitment until there is at least 1 certified rater for each assessment.

At each site there will be at least one senior clinician who will be responsible for (i) overseeing that all raters complete their training, (ii) being a resource to clinical raters with respect to scoring and rating and also for managing participant responses that need further review and (iii) ensuring that all new raters who join the projects at a later date complete the required training. The senior clinician will ensure that all raters have some familiarity with the measures either by reviewing them or observing more senior or trained raters prior to the official training. The senior clinician will lead the rater training activities at each site as outlined in the training plan for each measure described in the sections below.

All training sessions will be completed virtually. Recorded sessions and all slides presented by trainers during the training session will be available immediately after in a library of resources. Initial training for all measures will occur prior to startup. All training procedures must be followed by all new raters who join later.

Summary of Responsibilities

Role	Responsibility
Study PI/Training Lead	Oversee training program and certify interviewers
Trainers	Conduct training sessions and rate reliability/provide feedback for attaining certification/conduct consensus calls
Trainees	Attend training, complete assessments, and achieve certification/reliability

Clinical Training SOPs

This SOP outlines standardized training procedures for the administration, scoring, and interpretation of the assessor administered clinical rating scales. Any deviations from this SOP must be documented and approved by the study PI. Corrective actions (e.g., retraining) must be recorded.

PSYCHS-CT

The PSYCHS-CT SOP outlines the standardized training procedures for the administration, scoring, and interpretation of the *Positive SYmptoms and Diagnostic Criteria for the CAARMS Harmonized with the SIPS* (PSYCHS-CT) interview. This ensures interrater reliability, fidelity to the manual, and adherence to research or clinical protocol. The SOP applies to all clinicians, research assistants, or other personnel responsible for administering or scoring the PSYCHS-CT within clinical, research, or clinical trial settings. Key trainers will be Dr. Barbara Walsh and Dr. Scott Woods. Dr Scott Woods is one of the developers of the SIPS. Drs Woods and Walsh, along with AMPSCZ colleagues, developed the new instrument PSYCHS-CT.

1. Required Training Materials

- PSYCHS-CT Interview Assessment
- PSYCHS-CT manual (latest version)
- Training slide deck
- Sample interview videos with scoring keys

2. Training Components

2.1 Didactic Instruction (2–4 Hours)

- Overview of CHR criteria and harmonization goals
- Structure and domains of the PSYCHS-CT
- Anchor points and frequency/duration rules
- Scoring conventions and common rating errors
- Trainer leads Q&A session on ambiguous anchors and rules

2.2 Manual-Based Review (1–2 Hours)

- Trainees review the PSYCHS-CT manual independently

2.3 Interview Observation (4–6 Hours)

- Watch at least **3 gold-standard interviews**
- Score independently using PSYCHS-CT forms
- Participate in scoring calibration feedback call

3. Certification Procedures

3.1 New Raters, Either Central Raters or Site Raters

Requirement	Description
Rating Accuracy	The goal is to obtain all ratings in the correct range (normal/CHR/psychosis). For any items rated outside the correct range, calibration discussions between rater and trainer will probe for ability to correct ratings. If individuals can correct and articulate an understanding of why this is a better rating, they can become certified. If they can't calibrate during the discussion, it will be up to the judgment of the certifying trainer to determine if the rater can achieve certification with remedial intervention.
Conceptual Understanding	Demonstrates appropriate justification and adherence to anchor definitions
Interviewer Skills	Demonstrates ability to follow script, probe appropriately, and score in real-time

3.2 Previously Certified PSYCHS Raters

If rater previously successfully completed certification and re-certification process on the PSYCHS, then the rater will be asked to rate a PSYCHS-CT interview vignette. If the rater was previously certified but did not complete the recertification process, then they will be required to watch and rate an additional video. In either case, the rater must achieve the requirements described in section 3.1.

4. Ongoing Reliability Monitoring

- Participate in Consensus Calls (frequency to be determined) to present vignettes on completed PSYCHS assessments to determine eligibility, to provide opinion on agreement of ratings and to present vignettes on any ongoing cases that meet conversion criteria. These calls will serve to provide ongoing training on accurately rating and diagnosing with the PSYCHS-CT and promote inter-rater reliability.
- Remediation required for any rater falling below threshold
- Recertification will occur at the one-year timepoint of the study. This process will involve the rating of an additional video, following the same rating accuracy as outlined in the initial certification process.

PANSS

The PANSS SOP outlines the procedures for training and certifying raters administering the Positive and Negative Syndrome Scale (PANSS) in a drug trial targeting individuals at Clinical High Risk (CHR) for psychosis. Training will be conducted by Dr. Barbara Walsh. Trainees will be all central raters who will be administering or scoring the PANSS.

1. Required Materials

- SCI-PANSS Interview Guide (Structured Clinical Interview for PANSS)
- PANSS Manual with item anchors
- PANSS rating forms and scoring templates
- PANSS CHR-relevant vignette

- PANSS scoring conventions guide
- PANSS rater training slide deck

2. Didactic Training

- Overview of the PANSS: Structure and subscales (Positive, Negative, General Psychopathology)
- Anchoring definitions and item-by-item rating conventions
- Scoring rules, basis of ratings (interview vs. collateral), and handling ambiguity
- CHR-specific considerations (e.g., attenuated symptoms, functional decline)
- Independent scoring for certification of one CHR vignette
- Submit scores for review
- $\geq 80\%$ agreement with gold standard required for certification

3. CERTIFICATION

Requirement	Description
Accuracy	Minimum of 80% item-level agreement with gold standard for 2 full interviews
Documentation	Completed scoring sheets submitted and filed
Approval	Certification signed off by Lead PANSS trainer

4. MAINTENANCE OF CERTIFICATION

- Re-certification required for one CHR vignette every 12 months
- Re-training required if PANSS is not used for >3 months

Negative Symptom Inventory-Psychosis Risk (NSI-PR)

The NSI-PR SOP outlines the standardized procedures for training and certifying raters administering the *Negative Symptom Inventory-Psychosis Risk* (NSI-PR) interview in a drug trial targeting individuals at Clinical High Risk (CHR) for psychosis. The goal is to ensure interrater reliability and adherence to research or clinical protocol. Training of the central raters will be conducted by Dr. Greg Strauss of the University of Georgia. Dr Strauss is the developer of the NSI-PR and has many years' experience training on negative symptoms for a wide range of trials including pharmacological randomized control trials (RCT).

1. Required Training Materials

- Strauss, G. P., Walker, E. F., Carter, N. T., Luther, L., & Mittal, V. A. (2024). The Negative Symptom Inventory-Psychosis Risk (NSI-PR): Psychometric validation of the final 11-item version. *Schizophrenia Bulletin*. Advance online publication. <https://doi.org/10.1093/schbul/sbae206>
- NSI-PR Manual
- NSI-PR Interview Guide
- NSI-PR Scoresheet
- NSI-PR FAQ sheet
- NSI-PR Interview Assessment

- Training slide deck
- Mock interview video and corresponding transcript to use for rating submission

2. Training Components

2.1 Didactic Instruction (1.5 - 2 Hours)

- Overview of the NSI-PR: Structure, anchoring definitions, and item-by-item rating conventions
- Scoring rules, basis of ratings, and handling ambiguity
- Review certification steps and requirements

2.2 Practice (1-2 Hours)

- Practice administering the interview by completing mock and supervised mock sessions with supervisor or experienced rater
- Confirm high reliability with supervisor or experienced rater

2.3 Reliability Exercise for Certification (1 – 1.5 Hours)

- Watch training video and complete independent scoring of three mock cases
- Submit scores via provided form
- Raters who do not achieve rating accuracy criterion with initial 3 videos, will be required to review gold standard scores from the first 3 and discuss them with their clinical lead. Then view and score two additional videos that they rate on 2nd attempt.

3. Certification

Requirement	Description
Rating Accuracy	Meet a reliability threshold of ≥ 0.80 weighted kappa
Documentation	Completed scoring sheets submitted and filed
Approval	Certification signed off by Lead NSI-PR trainer

4. Maintenance of Certification

- Re-certification required for one vignette every 12 months
- Re-training required if NSI-PR not used for >3 months

Calgary Depression Scale (CDSS)

The CDSS SOP outlines the standardized procedures for training and certifying raters administering the *Calgary Depression Scale for Schizophrenia* (CDSS) interview in a drug trial targeting individuals at Clinical High Risk (CHR) for psychosis. The goal is to ensure interrater reliability and adherence to research or clinical protocol. Training of the central raters will be conducted by Dr. Monica Calkins, a ProCAN investigator at the University of Pennsylvania and Team B/I POP co-chair. Dr. Calkins has many years experience in assessment, training, and supervision for large consortia investigating psychosis and mood clinical phenotypes.

1. Required Training Materials

- Addington, J., Shah, H., Liu, L., & Addington, D. (2014). Reliability and validity of the Calgary Depression Scale for Schizophrenia (CDSS) in youth at clinical high risk for

psychosis. *Schizophrenia Research*, 153(1–3), 64-67. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.schres.2013.12.014>

- CDSS Interview Assessment
- Training slide deck
- Mock interview video and corresponding transcript to use for rating submission

2. Training Components

2.1 Didactic Instruction (1 Hour)

- Overview of the CDSS: Structure, anchoring definitions, and item-by-item rating conventions
- Scoring rules, basis of ratings, and handling ambiguity
- CHR-specific considerations
- Review certification steps and requirements
 - Independent scoring for certification of one vignette
 - Submit scores for review
 - Certification requires no more than a 1-point difference on any item and at least 80% total score agreement with gold standard ratings

2.2 Practice (1-2 Hours)

- Practice administering the interview by completing mock and supervised mock sessions with supervisor or experienced rater
- Confirm high reliability with supervisor or experienced rater
 - A rater should develop adequate inter-rater reliability within 5 practice interviews

2.3 Reliability Exercise for Certification (30 Minutes - 1 Hour)

- Watch training video and complete scoring
- Submit scores via provided form

3. Certification

Requirement	Description
Rating Accuracy	Minimum of 80% item-level agreement with gold standard for one vignette to demonstrate adherence to anchor definitions
Documentation	Completed scoring sheets submitted and filed
Approval	Certification signed off by Lead CDSS trainer

4. Maintenance of Certification

- Re-certification required for one vignette every 12 months
- Re-training required if CDSS not used for >3 months

Columbia-Suicide Severity rating Scale (C-SSRS)

Central raters will complete the online training for the C-SSRS which is provided free by the Columbia Lighthouse Project and which provides proof of training. The Policy established by the Columbia Lighthouse Project is that the training certificate is valid for the duration of an ongoing trial where the scale is administered continuously. We therefore require training certificates to be completed ASAP for all raters which means that we will not have to monitor re-certification. Training certificates should be submitted to Adisa Velovic (avelovic@northwell.edu)

Remaining Measures (Self Report) to be covered in a 1- hour additional training session.

Training will be conducted by Dr. Barbara Walsh.

- Prior to the training session all senior clinicians and available raters will familiarize themselves with all self-report measures listed above. They will prepare a list of questions they might have on the administration of these measures.
- There will then be time for senior clinicians to ask any questions they may have on the self- report measures with Dr. Walsh.

Psychoeducation Training

The purpose of the Psychoeducation SOP is to ensure that all study personnel are trained to deliver consistent, accurate, and supportive psychoeducation to individuals meeting criteria for Clinical High Risk (CHR) for psychosis who are enrolled in a drug trial. This SOP outlines the standardized process for staff training and competency assessment, and applies to all clinical staff, research assistants, and study coordinators involved in psychoeducation delivery to CHR participants.

1. Training Objectives

Trainees will learn to:

- Understand CHR symptoms and developmental risk factors.
- Explain the purpose, design, and procedures of the drug trial clearly and ethically
- Explain that participation in psychoeducation is optional
- Deliver structured psychoeducation modules covering:
 - CHR symptoms and risk status
 - Medication rationale and adherence strategies
 - Trial participation expectations
 - Coping strategies and self-monitoring
- Tailor delivery to developmental level and cultural background of participants.
- Support participant autonomy and engagement.

2. Training Components

2.1 Pre-Training Preparation

- Staff review training materials:
 - CHR psychoeducation manual
 - Study protocol and consent form
 - Sample scripts and handouts
 - Adherence and safety plan overview

2.2 In-Person/Virtual Training Workshop (3 hours)

Topics Covered:

- Overview of CHR and role of psychoeducation

- Overview of drug trial and participant flow
- Detailed walkthrough of psychoeducation sessions (modular content)
- Addressing common participant questions
- Ethical considerations and maintaining rapport

2.3 Competency Evaluation

- Trainees complete a mock delivery of psychoeducation to a trainer
- Trainer evaluates using a standardized checklist (e.g., content accuracy, empathy, clarity).
- Staff must score $\geq 80\%$ to be approved for unsupervised delivery.

3. Supervision and Ongoing Support.

- Annual refresher required or as needed following protocol amendments.

4. Documentation Requirements

- Training attendance logs
- Competency evaluation forms
- Supervision observation checklists
- Refresher session logs

All training documents must be stored in the site regulatory binder and staff training folder.

5. Quality Assurance

- Random audits of psychoeducation documentation
- Remediation plan for staff who do not meet training standards

6. References

- CHR Psychoeducation Manual
- Study Protocol
- IRB-Approved Informed Consent Form
- Good Clinical Practice (GCP) Guidelines

Consensus Diagnostic Calls

There will be one consensus call led by Dr. Walsh across the network. All raters, both site and central, involved in completing the PSYCHS for ascertainment/transition will attend regular zoom calls to determine by consensus that participants meet entry/conversion criteria. Prior to each call a standard vignette will be circulated to the group in which the site is participating. Each vignette, which will report on inclusion and exclusion criteria and describe all measurement concepts for the PSYCHS ratings, will be reviewed so that consensus on meeting criteria is made for every participant included. The expectation is that senior clinicians at each site will have reviewed the vignette prior to submission to the consensus group. Even if a rater is not presenting a vignette, it is expected that they will attend the call for ongoing training and to ensure interrater reliability. Central raters will also be expected to attend these calls to express their consensus with the eligibility ratings.

When a participant is thought to have made the transition to psychosis, a vignette detailing the transition will also be prepared by the central rater and the above procedure for consensus will also be followed.

Quality Control of Clinical Data

The ProCAN data collection team will monitor the collection of data at all data points. Reasons for missing

data will be reviewed and discussed with sites. Monitoring and extensive automated QA/QC of data within and across data collection forms, i.e., cross checking measures, outlier detection, will be the responsibility of the CT-DPACC. The QC procedures completed by the CT-DPACC will be developed and documented in an additional QC document. In addition to automatic checks, CT-DPACC will conduct on-site monitoring visits, where essential items will be checked for 100% of the subject sample (e.g. eligibility, informed consent, safety, study medication accountability and titration, the primary outcome measure). In addition, all source documentation (e.g. notes in medical files, paper documents, drug accountability forms) will be checked for 25% of the subject sample. Monitoring procedures are described in detail in the Monitoring Plan.

One important exception to the procedures described above is the QC for the PSYCHS-CT (Clinical Trial), which is overseen by Drs. Barbara Walsh and Scott Woods. When systematic errors are noticed during consensus calls (within 1 specific symptom) and/or too many errors are made (across the scale), the transcripts of the interviews can be used for a cross check with the scores as entered into Redcap. These transcripts are applied as a tool for further investigation and to obtain insight into what the underlying problem is for the incorrect scoring if this cannot be gained from the discussion during the consensus call.

A cross check between the transcript and the scores as entered in RedCAP are indicated in the following cases:

- A deviation of 2 or more points on a symptom, and the underlying problem cannot be understood and resolved during the consensus call.
- Repeated deviations of 1 point on a specific symptom across the rater group or within 1 rater - this would suggest a systematic issue and may warrant further investigation.
- A faulty conclusion/diagnosis of 'CHR' (at screening) or 'transition' (during the study), which cannot be understood and resolved based on the info provided by the rater during the consensus call.

Central Rater Scheduling

Guidelines have been established for scheduling and conducting Central Rater assessments for the ProCAN study, leveraging HIPAA-compliant Zoom video conferencing to maintain the highest standards of participant privacy and data security.

1. Central Rater Assessments Visit:

- Central Raters will assess clinical symptoms as described in the protocol schedule of activities.
- The visit will take place using HIPAA-compliant Zoom.
- The central rater assessments can be scheduled before or after the on-site assessments.
- Once the visit is completed, the central rater will provide the “Safety Assessment Form” via REDCap (or email if REDCap is not available). This form will indicate if there are any safety concerns and will need to be signed off by the site staff.

2. Site Staff Responsibilities During the Visit:

- Site staff must start the video call at the beginning of the visit.
- Site staff must join back at the end of the visit to conclude the call.
- Each site will follow the designated site “Clinical Assessment Safety Plan” if needed.

3. Scheduling the Zoom Assessment:

- Site staff will be given access to complete a “Zoom Assessment Scheduling Form”.
- The following information will need to be provided on the form:
 - o Participant information (Study ID and pseudo name for the central rater to use)
 - o Type of visit (visit week)
 - o Study staff contact information (in case of emergency)
 - o Some basic patient health information which does not include PHI
 - o Any additional information the central rater should know prior to the assessment. Site will

make sure this does not include any PHI

- The next page of the scheduling form will provide the link to the Zoom booking page.
 - On the booking page:
 - Select an available time slot
 - Enter the following information:
 - ❖ “First Name”: enter subject’s study ID
 - ❖ “Last Name”: enter site staff’s last name
 - ❖ “Email Address”: enter site staff email
 - Click “book” to finalize the appointment.
 - The listed site staff will receive an email confirmation with the zoom link.
4. Booking System Guidelines:
- a. The calendar invite and virtual meeting link will be sent only to the site staff listed on the Zoom booking page. Do not forward this invite to the participant.
 - b. Site staff must open the link and start the meeting.
 - c. The participant should be in a private space at the site for the meeting.
 - d. Site staff will be alerted when the virtual visit is nearing completion and must rejoin the call to end it.
 - e. The booking system accommodates different time zones, so available times will be displayed in the site's local time zone.
 - f. Crucially: Enter only site staff name and email on the booking page; do not enter patient information.
4. Cancellations and No-Shows:
- Sites must confirm the visit with the participant beforehand.
 - If a visit is canceled, notify the ProCAN project manager, Adisa Velovic (avelovic@northwell.edu) as soon as possible.

References for Clinical Measures

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